

Globus: moving large volumes of research data with ease

Welcome!

The webinar starts at 12pm AEST/ 11:30am ACST/ 10am AWST

Australian **BioCommons**

Actively supporting Australian life sciences research through
bioinformatics and bioscience data infrastructure

biocommons.org.au

Follow us on:

Acknowledgement of Country

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and their custodianship of the lands on which we meet today.

We pay our respects to their Ancestors and their descendants, who continue cultural and spiritual connections to Country.

We recognise their valuable contributions to Australian and global society.

WEBINAR

Globus: moving research data with ease

Greg D'Arcy
AARNet

Dr Farah Zaib Khan
Australian BioCommons

Greg D'Arcy
AARNet

Dr Farah Zaib Khan
Australian BioCommons

John Pearson
QIMR Berghofer

Dr Rohan Lowe
La Trobe University

Hello!

I am Farah Zaib Khan

I am part of engagement team at
Australian BioCommons

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GENOMICS

HUMAN GENOME INFORMATICS

METABOLOMICS

MICROBIOME ANALYSIS

PROTEOMICS

SINGLE CELL AND SPATIAL OMICS

MULTI-OMICS ANALYSIS

BIOINFORMATIC WORKFLOWS

COMPUTATIONAL STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY

BioCommons engages with:

Methods based communities

- genomics
- single cell omics
- metabolomics
- multi-omics
- proteomics
- microbiome analysis

Research consortia

Data production facilities

Recurrent challenge emerged across all domains we engaged
with:

Omic Data Movement at Scale

Today's Webinar

Context & Complexity: The Data Movement Crisis

Reductions in DNA sequencing costs have outpaced Moore's Law for nearly two decades, driving biology into the "Zettabyte Era."

Cost per Raw Megabase of DNA Sequence

Cost per Human Genome

Source: <https://www.genome.gov/about-genomics/fact-sheets/DNA-Sequencing-Costs-Data>

Context & Complexity: The Data Movement Crisis

Evolution of sequencing technologies are generating data at exponential rates, creating a “data deluge.”

First-Gen Sequencing (Sanger era)

- Slow, manual processes
- **MB-scale datasets**
- Local analysis possible

Data growth: *LOW*

High-throughput NGS expansion

- Population-scale genomics
- Multi-omics begins (RNA-seq, metagenomics)
- **TB → PB-scale datasets**

Data growth: *VERY HIGH*

Current era: Data Deluge

- PB → EB-scale datasets
- Data cannot be easily moved between infrastructures
- Compute often waits for data

2005

Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS)

- Parallel sequencing introduced
- **GB → TB-scale datasets**
- Routine genome sequencing begins

Data growth: *HIGH (10–100x increase)*

2015

Multi-omics + population-scale projects

- Large consortia (human, microbiome, environmental)
- Continuous data generation
- Storage + transfer pressures emerge

Data growth: *EXPONENTIAL*

2025+

Context & Complexity: The Data Movement Crisis

We have solved the problem of Data Generation - at a massive scale
Now the limiting factor is Data Movement

Context & Complexity: The Data Movement Crisis

Legacy methods - **NOT** built for today's data volumes, distances or scientific demands

SLOW TRANSFERS

Latency kills performance

Long distance cause delays that stall research results

UNRELIABILITY

Connection drops require manual restarts

Failed transfers waste time and jeopardise data integrity

COMPLEXITY

Security barriers block collaboration

Rigid firewall and VPN configurations slow down innovation

INEFFICIENCY

Wasted researchers time

Long distance cause delays that stall research results

Need for better data movement methods

If not legacy data transfer methods, then what?

Need for better data movement methods

Let's hear from our esteemed speakers

Dr Rohan Lowe

Bioinformatician
La Trobe University

Use case: Moving proteomics data to the [PRIDE](#) repository

John Pearson

Manager
Genome Informatics Group,
QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute

Use case: Securely share data with collaborators in Australia and globally

Downloading ENA data at Scale via Globus

API USAGE (PER MONTH)

ENA PORTAL (ADVANCED SEARCH) API

28
MILLION
REQUESTS

57k
UNIQUE
HOSTS

1.6 TB
METADATA
SERVED

ENA BROWSER API

90+
MILLION
REQUESTS

62k
UNIQUE
HOSTS

3.3 TB
METADATA &
DATA SERVED

FASTQ FILES FOR DOWNSTREAM ANALYSIS (12 MONTHS)

73.6%

OF GENERATED FASTQ FILES ENABLING
DOWNSTREAM ANALYSIS WITH HIGH-
QUALITY DATA

DATA DOWNLOADS (12 MONTHS)

52.22 PB

TOTAL DATA DOWNLOADED
FROM ENA SERVER

aspera
an IBM® company

Downloading ENA data at Scale via Globus

Accessing ENA Data

Connect to the [EMBL-EBI Public Data endpoint](#) and navigate to the `/vo11` subfolder.

Integration Options

- [Globus CLI](#) & [Globus Connect Personal](#)
- [Transfer APIs](#)
- [Python](#) & [JavaScript](#) Software Development Kits (SDKs)

Recommended for Large Dataset downloads

ENA recommends Globus for large or multi-file transfers:

- Superior throughput
- Robust error handling
- Auto-resume capabilities

Sources:

- [10.1093/nar/gkaf1295](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295)
- <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/retrieval/file-download.html#using-globus>

Globus: orchestrating data-intensive research at scale

Let's hear from our speaker

Greg D'Arcy

Digital Research Product Manager
AARNet

GLOBUS FILE UPLOAD TO PROTEOMICS DATA REPOSITORIES

Dr Rohan Lowe
**La Trobe University Proteomics and
Metabolomics Platform**

Email: pmp@latrobe.edu.au

PROTEOMICS & METABOLOMICS PLATFORM

– WHAT WE DO

Prof David Greening
Director Proteomics &
Metabolomics Platform

- Analytical instrumentation and expertise to characterise molecules.
- University context, work with many different project types

Proteomics

Dr Rohan Lowe

Dr Bushra Amin

- Protein identification/quant
- Biomarker discovery, drug QA
- Bioinformatics, scripting
- LC-MS, SPR

Metabolomics

Dr Thy Truong

Dr Jing Cui

- Metabolite identification/quant
- LC-MS, GC-MS, UV-Vis
- Bioinformatics

Small Molecule Structure (NMR)

Daniela Briceño

- Structural analysis of small molecules
- High-res and high-throughput mass-spec
- *quantitative metabolomics*
- NMR, LC-MS

PROTEOMICS PUBLISHING AND DATA SHARING

- **PROTEOMICS JOURNAL INSTRUCTIONS FOR AUTHORS:**
“STATING THAT DATA ARE AVAILABLE ON A REASONABLE REQUEST IS NOT ACCEPTABLE.”
- **PRIDE-PROTEOME EXCHANGE FOR DATA SHARING**
- **SUBMISSIONS CAN BE 100’S OF GB AND 100’S OF FILES IN A LARGE PROJECT. (12GB/H PER INSTRUMENT)**
- **EBI SERVERS ARE FAR AWAY (UK), OFTEN ARE HARD TO SEND DATA TO.**
- **I WORK IN A UNIVERSITY. CONNECTIVITY IS USUALLY OK, BUT MAY BE IN THE 10’S OF MBIT.**

Home PRIDE Archive Affinity Proteomics Archive PRIDE USI PRIDE Proteins Tools and Services Help About

PRIDE is the data repository

5000 datasets per year

Mission

The ProteomeXchange Consortium was established to provide globally coordinated standard data submission and dissemination pipelines involving the main proteomics repositories, and to encourage open data policies in the field. Please review our [Data Submission Guidelines](#), [Guidelines for Reprocessed datasets](#) and [PX Membership Agreement](#).

See also the [original Nature Biotechnology publication](#) and the [2017](#), [2020](#) and [2023](#) update papers.

Proteome Exchange is a consortium who developed the framework for proteomics data sharing

PROBLEMS

PRIDE SUBMISSION JAVA APP

DEFAULT UPLOAD MODES ARE FTP AND ASPERA

FUNCTIONAL BUT SLOW, DIFFICULTIES WITH BAD OR SLOW CONNECTIONS.

THE PROCESS IS COMPLEX AND NOT VERY USER FRIENDLY, SO IT HURTS WHEN IT FAILS.

PRIDE Submission Tool Version - 2.7.3

Step 9: Submission Summary (9/10)

Please double-check before starting your submission

Proteome Xchange

Total file count: 10 Result files: 0 Raw files: 7 [Export submission.px](#)

Peak files: 1 Search files: 1 Other files: 1

File ID	File Name	Type	File Size(bytes)
0	checksum.txt	OTHER	1047
358	txt.tar	SEARCH	146532864
360	PHAXRNASE_240111_1_HFX240207_A_SRP...	RAW	1099061803
361	PHAXRNASE_240111_1_HFX240207_A_SRP...	RAW	1093210800
362	PHAXRNASE_240111_1_HFX240207_A_SRP...	RAW	1089100894
363	PHAXRNASE_240111_1_HFX240207_A_SRP...	RAW	1116920819

Select Upload Method: FTP ASPERA

Please accept [PRIDE Archive dataset license](#) and also read [PRIDE data policy](#)

[?](#) [Cancel](#) [Back](#) [Submit](#)

GLOBUS AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO FTP/ASPERA

- **WHAT IS GLOBUS?**

- File transfers, sharing, compute, apps etc.
- University of Chicago initiative

- **FILE TRANSFERS PRINCIPLE**

- Secure, reliable.
- Set-and-forget, Globus resumes and checks during any interruptions
- Web or command line
- Subscriptions are for organizations, not individuals.
- Non-profits can get free transfers, eg uni post-docs, students.

- **THE EBI OFFERS A GLOBUS TRANSFER ENDPOINT FOR PRIDE PROTEOMICS UPLOADS**

Login to app with EBI user credentials.
Fill out metadata and file details in the app

Choose FTP or ASPERA upload

Run upload in the java app

Wait 4 hours and hope

Failure

Success

manual

Login to app with EBI user credentials.
Fill out metadata and file details in the app

Export the "Submission.px" file and checksum.txt file

Login at ebi.ac.uk/pride
Select "new submission"

Provide your Globus.org username

Receive your globus folder ID by email

Install Globus Connect Personal software

Upload all files via Globus web

Failure

Success

auto

WHAT WAS THE EXPERIENCE LIKE?

- **PX-SUBMISSION APP UPLOAD WAS PREDICTING A 2-3 H UPLOAD FOR A SMALL PROJECT OF JUST ~ 20GB (~ 20-30 MBIT/S)**
- **I HAD ALREADY HEARD OF THE GLOBUS OPTION**
- **STOPPED THE PX UPLOAD AND STARTED TO READ HOW TO USE GLOBUS**
- **REGISTERED, INSTALLED THE SOFTWARE.**
- **RAN THROUGH THE TUTORIAL**
- **STARTED THE PRIDE GLOBUS UPLOAD OPTION**
- **COMPLETED SEAMLESSLY, WITH DROP-OUTS CORRECTED**
- **WHOLE PROCESS TOOK FAR LESS TIME THAN THE PREDICTION FOR THE ORIGINAL METHOD.**
- **AN IDEAL OPTION FOR 'POWER' USERS**

ANY NEGATIVES?

- **FIRST RUN THOUGH WAS A BIT TECHNICAL AND REQUIRED MORE WORK**
 - **INSTALLATION OF NEW SOFTWARE**
- **GLOBUS IS NOT AN OBVIOUS OPTION FOR THIS PROCESS.**

SOME FEEDBACK FROM A CLIENT:

“QUITE DIFFICULT”

“MANAGED TO FIGURE IT OUT BY FOLLOWING THE TUTORIAL, THE GLOBUS 'HOW TO', AND CHATGPT.”

EBI's PRIDE:Globus explainer

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/markdownpage/globus>

<https://www.globus.org/>

SUMMARY

GLOBUS IS A MODERN FILE TRANSFER TECHNOLOGY FOR PROTEOMICS DATA UPLOAD TO PRIDE

ROBUST AND FAST ONCE SETUP

MORE TECHNICAL VS FTP OR ASPERA

SPEED BENEFIT CAN NEGATE THE EXTRA TRAINING REQUIREMENT

Email La Trobe PMP

pmp@latrobe.edu.au

Browse our website

latrobe.edu.au/proteomics

QIMR
Berghofer

QIMRB SeqHaven Project Sharing Genomes

John Pearson, QIMR Berghofer

BioCommons Webinar

2026-05-13

Genomics – Data Scale

1 Human genome

100 GBytes

1 Cancer patient

300 GBytes

1 Study (100 patients)

30 TBytes

1 Study (new technology)

0.5 PBytes

SeqHaven

SeqHaven – Why Globus?

University of Chicago – made for academics

Longevity – Globus toolkit first released in 1998

Widely used – 1,500 organisations in 80 countries

Local use – UQ, QUT, NCI, Pawsey, CSIRO, UWA, MCRI

Local support - AARNET

Web, CLI, API access

Clients don't need a license

Freemium model for server

SeqHaven – So Far

3 pilot data transfers – USA, Sweden, WA

2 out of 3 organisations had Globus servers

Some learning required & significant negotiation with local IT

Not just for data distribution – collaboration!

SeqHaven – Future

Globus Flows

- Complex workflows
- Event driven – file creation etc
- Internal scheduling – regular data transfers / backups

Globus Connectors

Thank you

john.pearson@qimrb.edu.au

Globus: orchestrating data-intensive research at scale

Greg D'Arcy, AARNET

Wednesday 13 May 2026

Globus @AARNet

Our Shareholders

37 Australian Universities
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National Network

International Network

NREN Community

“

Highly connected, accessible, reliable access to infrastructure and data within Australia and out to the world, so researchers can focus on the science rather than moving data.

”

The impact of data mobility on scientific research

PAIN POINTS

- TBs of data coming off instruments
- Pace of research (collaboration & global)
- Researchers still using old tools
- Cyber security, ethical & legal compliance

USE CASES

- Share data with collaborators
- Repatriate data to home institution
- Deposit raw data in global repository
- Download reference data from global repository
- Collect data to train AI models

Globus.org

- Developed by the University of Chicago in 1997, **Globus operates as a non-profit service** that has been widely adopted across major research facilities and research communities in the US.
- **Globus.org is a secure, cloud-based service** for automating and managing data transfers (terabytes to petabytes) across institutional and geographic boundaries.
- It provides a **single interface for accessing data stored across various systems**, from personal laptops to high-performance computing clusters, and simplifies the **movement of large datasets between instruments, storage systems and computing environments.**

Globus core features & functions

Globus platform for researchers

Data Transfer & Sharing

Publication & Discovery

Unified Data Access

Platform-as-a-Service

Remote Execution

Reliable Automation

Globus secure data transfer

- Fast, secure, and reliable **transfer of large datasets across institutions and systems.**
- “Fire-and-forget” transfers with **automatic retry and resume** after interruptions.
- Direct **endpoint-to-endpoint movement**, so data does not have to pass through your desktop.
- Optional **encryption in transit**, plus integrity checks to verify files arrive correctly.
- **Single sign-on with institutional credentials** and **fine-grained access controls** for sharing.
- Web and command-line access, with **monitoring, notifications, and scheduling/automation options.**

Major components of the Globus Connect Server

Globus Connect Server Architecture

Globus Connect Personal

- **Globus Connect Personal (GCP)** lets an individual researcher turn a laptop or desktop into a Globus collection, making it easy to move, sync, and share data without IT installing a full server endpoint.
- Works well for **moving data between a personal machine and campus or cloud storage**, including downloading data to a laptop.
- It is a **single-user endpoint**, so it is not a good fit for shared lab servers, department storage, or multi-user research computing systems.
- Install on Windows, macOS, and Linux.

Authentication

Log-in using your **institutional credentials** or select one of the three **alternative identity providers**, i.e. GitHub, Google or ORCID.

File Manager - <https://app.globus.org>

Move, share, & discover data via a single interface.

Transfer files between trusted endpoints.

NAME	LAST MODIFIED	SIZE
100G.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
100M.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
10G.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
10M.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
1G.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
1M.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
500G.dat	4/5/2024, 03:3...	
500GB-in-large-files	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
50G.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
50GB-in-medium-files	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
50M.dat	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
5GB-in-small-files	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
5MB-in-tiny-files	4/5/2024, 03:2...	
Climate-Huge	8/15/2024, 02...	

NAME	LAST MODIFIED	SIZE
1G.dat	3/1/2024, 09:...	1 GB
1M.dat	7/26/2024, 11...	1 MB
3G-md.xt	7/21/2022, 09...	1.83 GB
5MB-in-tiny-files	3/1/2024, 09:...	-
Data.zip	10/5/2023, 01...	4 GB
nf-core-workshop.tar.gz	5/2/2023, 09:...	1.28 GB
rnaseq_4.1.0.sif	7/5/2024, 12...	1.96 GB
test_rx	6/24/2024, 11...	-
test.txt	6/24/2024, 11...	32 B

Globus Automation Capabilities

Timer Service

Scheduled and recurring transfers (*a.k.a. Globus cron*)

Command Line Interface

Ad hoc scripting and integration

Globus SDK

Powerful integration using Python

Globus Flows

Comprehensive distributed task orchestration (data and compute) with human in the loop interactions

Globus Compute

Secure remote code execution and job scheduling

Automating Instrument Data Acquisition using Flows & Timers

Slide provided courtesy of Jack Bryant, Solutions Architect. University of Western Australia

Globus Flows

What is a Flow?

A sequence of steps...

- **Hosted**
- **Reusable**
- **Flexible**
- **Shareable**

A Flow is a sequence of steps (AWS Step Function based) or Actions...

What's an Action?

Each step in the flow is an *action*

- **Action calls other services to perform some operation**
 - E.g. move data, get a persistent identifier, send email to curator
- **Flows service manages interactions**
 - Authenticate, authorize, validate, store, auto-retry

Globus Flows for reliable, distributed automation

- Managed reliable **task orchestration**
- **Declarative language** for flow definition
- **Event driven** execution model
- **Extensible** to integrate external services

Examples of Flows

Two Stage Globus Transfer

- ✓ Temporarily transfer to an intermediate location before transferring to a destination

Move (Copy and Delete)

- ✓ After transferring to a destination, cleans up the files on the source

Transfer and Set Permissions

- ✓ After transferring to a destination, share with users and groups

Globus Compute

In the traditional model of remote computing...

- **Figure out authentication** (across multiple domains)
- Establish and maintain the right **network connections** (e.g., SSH)
- **Interact with resources** (configure for job scheduler, wait in queues, scale nodes)
- **Configure execution environments**
- **Detect, understand, and recover from various failures**
- ...

Researchers need to overcome the same obstacles every time they move to a new resource

Managed Compute ...on any system

- Support use of **Python for functions**
- **Fire and forget function execution**
- **Federated authentication**, and local access control
- **Uniform interface** to various compute resources

Interactive computing via familiar tools

- **No terminal login required, or scheduler specific scripts**
- Define function like any other code, and **code is run on compute resource**
- Use with **JupyterNB, Python applications**

```
# Define the function for remote execution
def hello_name(name: str):
    return f'Hello, {name}!'

from globus_compute_sdk import Client, Executor

MY_COMPUTE_ENDPOINT = "ad4f48be-9c03-49bc-9dc4-e240bc599bef"
compute_executor = Executor(endpoint_id=MY_COMPUTE_ENDPOINT)

# Run the function on the remote compute resource
my_result = compute_executor.submit(hello_name, 'you')

print(my_result)
```

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Globus Flows & Compute for Data Hygiene

Slide provided courtesy of Jack Bryant, Solutions Architect. University of Western Australia

Resources & Support

Supporting data intensive research

FileSender

- Easy-to-use website that allows you to share and receive large files.
- The sender has full control over who can access the files and for which period of time.
- <https://filesender.aarnet.edu.au>

Globus

- Infrastructure solution supporting TBs of data coming off instruments.
- Unifies access to distributed compute and storage resources and supports the end-to-end automation of complex research flows.

Globus Resources

- [Globus.org - Guides and documentation](#)
- [Globus Compute docs](#)
- [AARNet Knowledge Base](#)
- [Community of Practice website](#) (see eResearch workshop materials)
- [Github repo](#)
- [YouTube - Globus Technical Catch-up recordings](#)
- [Globus data transfer nodes in Australia](#)
(NEW)

Globus Support

- **Service desk** - support@globus.org
- **Globus Technical Catch-ups / Office hours** (register on AARNet website)
- **DataMovers drop-in sessions** (register on AARNet website)
- **Slack channel** - [globus-community-Australasia](#) (on request)

Find out more

biocommons.org.au

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[AustralianBioCommons](https://www.linkedin.com/company/australianbiocommons)

[AustralianBioCommonsChannel](https://www.youtube.com/channel/AustralianBioCommonsChannel)

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The Australian BioCommons is enabled by NCRIS via
Bioplatforms Australia funding

